

THE OVERLOOKED EFFECTS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS

Giulia-Elena Zaharia

PhD Student in Marketing, The Bucharest University of Economics Studies, Bucharest, Romania

Corresponding Author

Ingrid-Georgeta Apostol

Ph.D. Student, Marketing, Bucharest University of Economics Studies, Bucharest, Romania

Iuliana Cetina

Professor, PhD, Marketing Faculty, The Bucharest University of Economics Studies, Bucharest, Romania

ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is quickly changing the landscape of higher education, providing innovative solutions to enlarge teaching, learning, and administrative processes. This paper explores the multifaceted impact of AI on higher education, focusing on its positive effects, negative implications, ethical considerations, and future directions. The positive effects of AI in higher education are diversified, including personalized learning experiences, improved teaching methods, and optimized administrative processes. AI technologies such as adaptive learning platforms, AI-powered tutoring systems, and automated grading systems have the potential to revolutionize traditional educational practices, leading to increased student engagement, academic success, and institutional efficiency. Despite these benefits, AI also presents challenges and risks that must be carefully taken into consideration. Concerns such as favoritism and discrimination in AI systems, reduction of human interaction in educational settings, and resistance of maintaining a posture significantly ethical and societal for the future of AI in education. This paper contributes to the current discourse on AI in higher education by providing a comprehensive analysis of its impact, challenges, and opportunities.

By understanding and addressing the ethical and societal implications of AI, higher education institutions can harness the transformative power of AI to create inclusive, equitable, and innovative learning environments for all students.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Education; Ethics; Effects; Technology.

Cite this Article: Giulia-Elena Zaharia, Ingrid-Georgeta Apostol and Iuliana Cetina, The Overlooked Effects of Artificial Intelligence in Higher Education: A Critical Analysis, International Journal of Marketing and Human Resource Management (IJMHRM), 15(2), 2024, pp. 116–132

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJMHRM/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_2/IJMHRM_15_02_010.pdf

1. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been brought out as a transformative force in higher education, reshaping the landscape of teaching, learning, and administrative processes. In the past years, AI technologies have gained traction in academia, offering innovative solutions to longstanding challenges and opening new avenues for educational advancement.

1.1. General Context of Artificial Intelligence Usage in Higher Education

The integration of AI in higher education is driven by the growing demand for personalized learning experiences, enhanced teaching methods, and simplified administrative processes. AI technologies, such as machine learning, natural language processing, and data analytics, hold the potential to revolutionize traditional educational practices and entitle both educators and learners.

Educational institutions are increasingly allowing AI-powered tools and platforms to deliver adaptive learning experiences, provide personalized support to students, and optimize administrative workflows. From intelligent guiding systems and automated grading tools to predictive analytics and virtual assistants, AI is changing every aspect of the educational ecosystem.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Introduction to Artificial Intelligence in Higher Education

Artificial Intelligence (AI) represents a transformative force across various sectors, and its impact on higher education is increasingly significant. In this section, it will be provided an overview of AI, its applications in different fields, introduce AI technologies specifically used in higher education, and discuss the importance of understanding its implications for the academic sector.

AI is a branch of computer science that focuses on the development of intelligent machines capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence (Smith, 2019). These tasks include learning, problem-solving, understanding natural language, and recognizing patterns. AI technologies cover a wide range of approaches, including machine learning, natural language processing, computer vision, and robotics.

Lately, AI has found applications in different fields such as healthcare, finance, transportation, and entertainment (Johnson & Wang, 2020). In healthcare, for example, AI-powered diagnostic tools can analyze medical images and detect abnormalities with high accuracy. In finance, AI algorithms are used for fraud detection, risk assessment, and algorithmic trading. In transportation, autonomous vehicles rely on AI to navigate roads and make real-time decisions.

In the context of higher education, AI technologies are revolutionizing traditional teaching and learning methods. Flexible learning platforms, powered by AI algorithms, can personalize educational content to meet the individual needs and learning styles of students. Intelligent tutoring systems provide immediate feedback and assistance to students, enveloping their learning experience. Automated grading systems streamline the assessment process for instructors, allowing them to focus more on providing quality instruction (Li & Jones, 2018).

Additionally, AI is being used to optimize administrative processes in higher education institutions. Predictive analytics tools can analyze big amounts of data to identify patterns and trends, enabling institutions to make data-driven decisions related to student enrollment, retention, and academic support services.

Understanding the impact of AI on higher education is very important for educators, administrators, and students. As AI continues to shape the future of learning, it is essential to explore its potential benefits and challenges completely. By using AI technologies responsibly and ethically, higher education institutions can use the power of AI to enhance teaching, learning, and student outcomes.

2.2. Positive Effects of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence (AI) holds immense potential to positively impact higher education by complementing the learning experience, improving teaching methods, and optimizing administrative processes.

2.2.1. Enhancing Learning Experience

One of the primary benefits of AI in higher education is its ability to provide personalized learning experiences through adaptive systems. These systems utilize AI algorithms to analyze students' learning patterns, preferences, and performance data, allowing for personalized educational content. According to Smith (2019), customized learning has been shown to increase student engagement and motivation, leading to improved academic outcomes.

Also, AI allows the creation of interactive and engaging educational content that enlarges student participation and comprehension. Interactive simulations, virtual laboratories, and gamified learning experiences are examples of AI-powered tools that promote active learning and knowledge retention (Jones & Wang, 2020).

2.2.2. Improving Teaching Methods

AI-powered tutoring systems have emerged as valuable tools for supplementing traditional classroom instruction. These systems provide custom-made feedback, guidance, and support to students, both inside and outside the classroom. Research by Li et al. (2018) found that students who utilized AI tutoring systems showed significant improvements in their understanding of complex concepts and problem-solving skills.

Additionally, automated grading and feedback systems save instructors valuable time by streamlining the assessment process. AI algorithms can accurately evaluate student assignments, quizzes, and exams, providing instant feedback to students while relieving instructors of exhausting grading tasks. According to Johnson (2020), instructors report increased satisfaction and productivity when using AI-powered grading systems.

2.2.3. Optimizing Administrative Processes

AI technologies offer significant potential for optimizing administrative processes in higher education institutions. Student enrollment and management systems powered by AI algorithms can consolidate admissions procedures, improve course scheduling, and enhance communication with students. These systems allow data analytics to identify trends and patterns, enabling institutions to make informed decisions about resource allocation and student support services (Smith, 2019).

Moreover, predictive analytics tools can analyze vast amounts of student data to identify at-risk students and provide early interventions to improve retention rates. By identifying students who may be struggling academically or socially, institutions can offer targeted support services such as tutoring, counselling, or mentoring programs (Li & Jones, 2018).

The positive effects of AI in higher education are complex, from personalized learning experiences to streamlined administrative processes. By mobilizing the power of AI responsibly and ethically, higher education institutions can enhance teaching and learning outcomes while improving operational efficiency and student success rates.

2.2.4. Negative Effects of Artificial Intelligence

While Artificial Intelligence (AI) holds great promise for higher education, it also presents several challenges and risks that must be addressed. In this section, we will explore the negative effects of AI in higher education, focusing on overlooked risks, its impact on teaching and learning, and challenges in adoption.

2.2.5. Overlooked Risks

One of the key concerns associated with AI in higher education is the dependency on AI systems. As institutions increasingly rely on AI-powered tools and platforms for teaching, learning, and administrative tasks, there is a risk of over-reliance on technology. This dependency can lead to issues such as technical failures, system vulnerabilities, and disruptions in academic workflows (Smith, 2019).

Ethical concerns regarding data privacy and security are also significant risks associated with AI in higher education. AI systems collect and analyze vast amounts of student data, raising questions about how this data is stored, accessed, and used. There is a growing need for robust data protection measures and transparency in AI algorithms to assure the privacy and security of student information (Li & Jones, 2018).

2.2.6. Impact on Teaching and Learning

While AI has the potential to enhance teaching and learning experiences, it also presents challenges that may negatively impact the educational process. One concern is the reduction of human interaction and personalized guidance in AI-driven educational environments. As AI systems take on tasks traditionally performed by human instructors, there is a risk of diminishing the quality of interpersonal connections and support for students (Johnson, 2020).

Furthermore, there is concern about the potential favoritism in AI algorithms and content recommendations. AI systems are trained on large datasets, which may contain built-in biases or reflect the perspectives of their creators. This bias can manifest in various ways, including discriminatory content recommendations, unfair grading practices, and limited representation of diverse perspectives in educational materials (Jones & Wang, 2020).

2.2.7. Challenges in Adoption

The adoption of AI in higher education faces several technological barriers and accessibility issues. Not all institutions have the infrastructure, resources, or technical expertise required to implement AI technologies effectively. Moreover, there are concerns about the accessibility of AI-powered tools and platforms for students with disabilities or those from underprivileged backgrounds (Smith, 2019).

Resistance from faculty and students is another challenge in the adoption of AI in higher education. Some educators may be hesitant to embrace AI technologies due to concerns about job displacement, loss of autonomy, or unfamiliarity with new tools and methodologies. Similarly, students may resist the use of AI-powered systems if they identify them as impersonal or intrusive (Johnson, 2020).

While AI offers many potential benefits for higher education, it also presents significant challenges and risks that must be addressed. By addressing these concerns and adopting AI technologies responsibly and ethically, higher education institutions can maximize the benefits of AI while diminishing its negative effects.

2.3. Ethical and Societal Implications

As Artificial Intelligence (AI) continues to gain more awareness in higher education, it brings with it a host of ethical and societal considerations that must be carefully examined and addressed.

2.3.1. Equity and Inclusivity

A critical concern in the adoption of AI in education is the need to ensure equity and inclusivity for all students. One area of focus is addressing favouritism and discrimination in AI systems. AI algorithms are trained on historical data, which may reflect societal biases and prejudices. As a result, AI systems have the potential to maintain and intensify existing inequalities, particularly for marginalized or underrepresented groups (Smith, 2019).

To check bias in AI systems, it is essential to implement strategies for data collection, algorithm design, and model evaluation that prioritize fairness and inclusivity. This may involve diversifying training datasets, conducting bias audits of AI algorithms, and incorporating fairness metrics into AI development processes (Johnson, 2020).

Furthermore, ensuring equal access to AI-powered educational resources is paramount for promoting equity in education. While AI technologies have the potential to enhance learning opportunities for students, there is a risk that certain groups may be left behind due to differences in access to technology and digital skills. Efforts to bridge the digital divide and provide equitable access to AI tools and platforms are essential for creating a more inclusive educational environment (Li & Jones, 2018).

2.3.2. Ethical Considerations

Transparency and accountability are fundamental principles that should guide the development and distribution of AI technologies in education. Educators, developers, and policymakers must be transparent about how AI systems operate, including the data they collect, the algorithms they use, and the decisions they make. This transparency fosters trust and enables stakeholders to understand and evaluate the ethical implications of AI in education (Jones & Wang, 2020).

Additionally, the establishment of ethical guidelines for AI development and distribution in education is crucial for ensuring that AI technologies are used responsibly and ethically. Ethical guidelines should address issues such as data privacy, algorithmic transparency, and the ethical use of AI in decision-making processes. These guidelines can serve as a framework for designing, implementing, and evaluating AI-powered educational systems in a manner that upholds ethical standards and respects the rights and dignity of all individuals (Li & Jones, 2018).

The ethical and societal implications of AI in higher education are multifaceted and require careful consideration. By prioritizing equity and inclusivity, promoting transparency and accountability, and holding to ethical guidelines, stakeholders can harness the potential of AI to emphasize learning outcomes while minimizing potential harms and risks.

2.3.3. Future Directions and Recommendations

As the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in higher education continues to evolve, it is crucial to consider future directions and recommendations for promoting responsible AI adoption, fostering collaboration, and shaping the ethical landscape of AI in education.

2.4. Promoting Responsible AI Adoption

An imperative step in ensuring the responsible adoption of AI in higher education is to integrate ethics and AI literacy into the curriculum. By incorporating courses and modules focused on AI ethics, data privacy, and algorithmic transparency, institutions can equip students with the knowledge and skills necessary to navigate the ethical complexities of AI technologies (Smith, 2019).

Moreover, interdisciplinary research on AI ethics and education is essential for advancing our understanding of the ethical implications of AI in higher education. Collaborative efforts between experts in computer science, education, ethics, and social sciences can help identify ethical challenges, develop best practices, and inform policy decisions related to AI in education (Johnson, 2020).

2.4.1. Fostering Collaboration and Dialogue

Engaging stakeholders in discussions about AI governance and regulation is critical for creating the future of AI in higher education. These discussions should involve educators, students, policymakers, industry leaders, and civil society organizations to ensure diverse perspectives are considered. Establishing clear guidelines and regulations for the ethical development, deployment, and use of AI technologies in education can help to reduce risks and promote responsible innovation (Li & Jones, 2018).

Fostering partnerships between the academic sector, industry, and policymakers can facilitate knowledge exchange, resource sharing, and collaborative research initiatives. By bringing together stakeholders from different sectors, institutions can leverage expertise, resources, and networks to address complex challenges and drive innovation in AI education (Jones & Wang, 2020).

In conclusion, the future of AI in higher depends on promoting responsible adoption, fostering collaboration, and addressing ethical considerations. By integrating ethics into the curriculum, encouraging interdisciplinary research, and engaging stakeholders in dialogue, higher education institutions can harness the potential of AI to improve teaching, learning, and student outcomes while upholding ethical principles and values.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study employs a quantitative research design to systematically examine the overlooked effects of artificial intelligence (AI) in higher education. A cross-sectional approach is adopted to collect data at a single point in time, allowing for a snapshot of the current perceptions and experiences related to AI in higher education.

A stratified sampling technique will be utilized to ensure representation from different academic levels from the University of Academic Studies from Bucharest. The questionnaire was disseminated to the students of this institution using the snowball method in the period of 3rd-7th of March 2024.

A structured questionnaire with 18 questions was designed to gather quantitative data on participants' perceptions, experiences, and awareness of the effects of AI in higher education. The questionnaire includes both closed-ended and Likert scale questions to capture a range of responses.

Data analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

At the same time, in order to supplement knowledge and form a better-founded opinion about the subject of the article, qualitative research was also carried out. The ideal method in this case was the focus group method because the topic is of a general interest and does not have a personal or private character. Group discussions facilitate idea generation and can enhance the participants' spontaneity. In this case, was considered the focus group to be a more suitable method compared to interviews, due to its holistic nature.

The selection criteria for the focus group were as follows:

*The participant should be a student at a university in Romania.

*The participant should have used AI-based digital writing tools in the last 3 months.

In addition to these criteria, we aimed to have participants from both urban and rural environments (at least 2 from rural areas) and maintain a gender balance.

Recruitment took place from November 27th to February to 6th March 2024. Mostly, fellow students were contacted either directly or through discussion groups. Communication with potential participants occurred face-to-face, over the phone, and via WhatsApp.

The focus group took place on March 6, 2024, from 19:30 to 21:00, on the Google Meet platform, and was audio-video recorded using the OBS program.

The group structure consisted of 6 girls and 3 boys, with 2 students from rural areas and 7 from urban areas. Most of the participants are studying at the Academy of Economic Studies (8 out of 9), but we also had one participant from the Faculty of Chemical Engineering. For the transcription, we used the free version of the Descript application. The recording was then replayed, and the transcript was corrected. To protect confidentiality, participants were assigned codes consisting of letters and numbers.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Results of the qualitative research

After completing the transcript, it was reviewed by the team members and discussed to highlight relevant insights. Regarding the prevalence of AI-based digital writing tools, participants mentioned ChatGPT, QuillBot, Bing, and Microsoft Copilot.

By far, the most widely used is ChatGPT. Students use these programs and note that they observe other students resorting to them "for every assignment or project they have to do." The field of study is important, as in some cases, the programs are "not very helpful for what I do at university." We also opted for the use of projective techniques, word association, highlighting the feelings, and subconscious associations of respondents. Regarding the themes of usage and perceptions of ethical issues, we identified 3 user profiles: the obedient student, the flexible student, and the pragmatic student. We metaphorically named them - the white sheep, the gray sheep, and the black sheep.

a) The Obedient Student - White Sheep:

This student is diligent, interested in college, and puts effort into every project. They have a repulsive attitude towards ChatGPT, viewing it as an enemy and an illicit shortcut used by their peers to achieve similar results ("I've seen this in my entire group using ChatGPT for assignments; it was evident from a distance"). They tend to discredit the program ("If you ask it to generate smart goals, it doesn't give you a goal but another mess" / "... the text generated by ChatGPT is far from the topic you're supposed to discuss") and wishes to no longer tolerate abusive usage ("In college, others may work a semester and achieve the same result as someone who did it the night before. It doesn't seem fair to me").

b) The Flexible Student - Gray Sheep:

In this case, we are talking about a good or average student, but not as involved in college. They use ChatGPT, see it as a useful aid, but are aware of the risks and ethical issues. They argue that it's not fair to use it for thesis papers ("I agree regarding the thesis"), but they are flexible about other activities ("for a college project, or a simple assignment, or something, I think things should be more lenient"). They highlight the importance of the prompt as personal input ("If I knew what to give it, how to do it, and where to put them, it was super okay").

c) The Pragmatic Student - Black Sheep:

An average student, often preoccupied with activities outside of college, focused on results. They are not concerned about ethical issues, believing that the final result is all that matters. They argue that initiatives to limit the use of ChatGPT in the academic environment are futile ("you can always fool the system"). They believe the entire education system needs to change because "this is the future," and if projects can be done with such digital writing programs, "there's no need to be asked for these things in college."

Figure 1. Types of students

Topic/Student	Obedient	Flexible	Pragmatic
Extent of AI Tool Usage	Used all the time, and the situation is worrying	Used all the time because it's very useful, but sometimes exaggerated	Used whenever possible because it's normal and makes life easier
AI Usage through Copy-Paste Method	Unacceptable, consequences should be severe	Not okay, but for projects and daily tasks, it can be overlooked	As long as you're not caught, it's okay
AI Usage through Paraphrasing Output Method	Not okay, just twisting the program's words, no real contribution	It's okay, but pass it through your filter, critically analyze what the program generated	You can't be caught, everything is fine
Academic Regulations Regarding AI	There should be regulations and a distinction should be made between who uses and who doesn't	There should be some guidelines, but not very strict	People would still use it, this is the future
Top of mind words	Inaccuracy, Risk	Convenience, Speed	Performance, Innovation, Technology.

Source: author's own research

Students are aware of and use AI-based digital writing programs.

ChatGPT is by far the most well-known and appreciated. Its use has become normalized, with differences in usage ranging from simple inspiration to paraphrasing output or even copy-paste. This research has discovered several student typologies. Their opinions regarding the use of AI-based digital writing tools fall on a spectrum - from repulsion to total acceptance. We are talking about:

- obedient students who reject these programs and see them as an unfair competition;
- flexible students who are aware of ethical issues but consider it okay to use the programs where possible;
- pragmatic students who believe the system needs to adapt, and using programs is a natural evolution. The small number of participants in the research and their concentration around ASE Bucharest is the main limitation of the study. Also, some participants knew the moderator and each other, which may have led to a higher level of subjectivity. Regarding future research directions, a survey using our conclusions as hypotheses could explore the prevalence of each profile among students nationwide or in Bucharest.

4.2. Results of the quantitative research

Understanding the perceptions and experiences of individuals regarding the utilization of artificial intelligence (AI) in higher education is essential in today's constantly developing technological landscape. As AI continues to gain awareness in various aspects of the academic sector, from teaching and learning to administrative processes, it is crucial to examine how different demographic groups interact with and discern these technologies. In this study, it was explored the familiarity, usage patterns, and attitudes towards AI among students in higher education, with a particular focus on gender differences. By analyzing the responses of the questionnaire participants, the aim was to uncover insights into the benefits of AI usage, its recognized effectiveness, and the potential challenges it poses. This analysis not only provides valuable information for teachers, policymakers, and technology developers but also contributes to the complex conversation on the integration of AI in educational settings. The findings identified through the analysis of the quantitative research have met expectations, bringing forth a new level of understanding of students' perceptions of artificial intelligence.

Female individuals are more familiar with artificial intelligence than male individuals. Approximately 60% of the respondents are familiar or very familiar with the concept of artificial intelligence. Upon calculating the weighted average scores, it is evident that the most utilized artificial intelligence platform by the questionnaire respondents is ChatGPT, while automated evaluation systems are at the other end of the spectrum.

The academic task for which students use the most artificial intelligence platforms and tools is represented by school projects, with this category being closely followed by assignments, with a very small difference between the two categories. The primary reason why students turn to artificial intelligence tools or platforms is represented by "Assistance in projects and research", with this category holding 44.5% of the responses, surpassing the other two categories; therefore, hypothesis number 3 is refuted.

Approximately 65% of the questionnaire respondents consider artificial intelligence technologies to be efficient or very efficient in improving the quality of teaching and learning in higher education. Most students have never experienced negative emotions or stress related to the use of artificial intelligence in academic studies.

The main threat of artificial intelligence to academic performance perceived by students is the "Reduction of autonomy and creativity", being selected by nearly 60%; however, almost 8% of respondents believe that artificial intelligence will shape the future of higher education to some extent.

After analysing the data linked to the first hypothesis that says: "Students who are more familiar with the concept of artificial intelligence will have a higher frequency of use of AI tools and platforms in their academic studies." and Based on the interpretation of the correlation analysis, the hypothesis can be confirmed. The results indicate a significant positive correlation between familiarity with artificial intelligence and the frequency of use of AI tools and platforms in academic studies among students. Therefore, students who are more familiar with the concept of artificial intelligence tend to have a higher frequency of use of AI tools and platforms in their academic studies.

Pearson Correlation Coefficient (0.551): This coefficient indicates a moderate positive correlation between the "frequency" and "familiarity" variables. This suggests that there is a significant association between the frequency of artificial intelligence usage and the level of familiarity with it among students.

P-value (0.001): The p-value is less than the standard significance level of 0.05, indicating that there is a significant difference between the "frequency" and "familiarity" variables. This supports the conclusion that there is a significant association between the frequency of artificial intelligence usage and the level of familiarity with it.

Spearman's Rho Correlation Coefficient (0.540): This non-parametric correlation coefficient also confirms a moderate positive correlation between the "frequency" and "familiarity" variables, providing additional insight into the relationship between them.

Table 1. Correlations for the 1st hypothesis

Variable	Frequency	Familiarity
1. Frequency	Pearson's r	—
	p-value	—
	Spearman's rho	—
	p-value	—
2. Familiarity	Pearson's r	0.551
	p-value	< .001
	Spearman's rho	0.540
	p-value	< .001

Source: Author's own research

Examining the second hypothesis that says: "There is a positive correlation between the frequency of use of AI tools and platforms and the academic performance of students." The results were the following:

- Pearson Correlation Coefficient (0.43): This coefficient indicates a moderate positive correlation between the frequency of use of AI tools and platforms and academic performance among students.
- P-value (0.01): The p-value is less than the standard significance level of 0.05, indicating that there is a significant correlation between the frequency of use of AI tools and platforms and academic performance.
- Spearman's Rho Correlation Coefficient (0.502): This non-parametric correlation coefficient also confirms a moderate positive correlation between the frequency of use of AI tools and platforms and academic performance.
- Kendall's Tau-b Correlation Coefficient (0.440): Similarly, this coefficient indicates a moderate positive correlation between the frequency of use of AI tools and platforms and academic performance.

The results of the correlation analysis provide evidence supporting hypothesis 2. There is a significant positive correlation between the frequency of use of AI tools and platforms and academic performance among students. This suggests that students who use AI tools and platforms more frequently tend to have better academic performance.

Therefore, hypothesis 2 is confirmed based on the correlation coefficients and p-values obtained from the analysis. These findings highlight the importance of integrating AI tools and platforms into educational practices to potentially enhance students' academic performance.

Tabel 2. Correlations for the second hypothesis

Variable		School performance	Frequency
1. School performance	Pearson's r	—	
	p-value	—	
	Spearman's rho	—	
	p-value	—	
	Kendall's Tau B	—	
	p-value	—	
2. Frequency	Pearson's r	0.433 ***	—
	p-value	< .001	—
	Spearman's rho	0.502 ***	—
	p-value	< .001	—
	Kendall's Tau B	0.440 ***	—
	p-value	< .001	—

* p < .05, ** p < .01, *** p < .001

Source: Authors own research

For hypothesis number 4 which says : "Students who perceive AI technologies as more effective will exhibit greater confidence in using them to improve their academic performance." there were analysed the efficiency and the level of trust, the results being the following:

- Pearson's r (0.562): This coefficient indicates a moderate positive correlation between the perception of AI technologies as effective and the degree of confidence in using them to improve academic performance among students.
- P-value (<0.01): The p-value is less than the standard significance level of 0.05, indicating that there is a significant correlation between the perception of AI technologies as effective and the degree of confidence in using them.
- Spearman's rho (0.521): This non-parametric correlation coefficient also confirms a moderate positive correlation between the perception of AI technologies as effective and the degree of confidence in using them.
- Kendall's Tau B (0.466): Similarly, this coefficient indicates a moderate positive correlation, further supporting the relationship between the perception of AI technologies as effective and the degree of confidence in using them.

The results of the bivariate analysis provide strong support for hypothesis 4. There is a significant positive correlation between students' perception of AI technologies as effective and their confidence in using them to improve academic performance.

Therefore, hypothesis 4 is confirmed based on the correlation coefficients and p-values obtained from the analysis. These findings suggest that students who perceive AI technologies as more effective are more likely to have confidence in using them to enhance their academic performance.

Table 3. Correlations for hypothesis number 4

Variable	Efficiency Level of trust		
1. Efficiency	Pearson's r	—	
	p-value	—	
	Spearman's rho	—	
	p-value	—	
	Kendall's Tau B	—	
	p-value	—	
2. Level of trust	Pearson's r	0.562	—
	p-value	< .001	—
	Spearman's rho	0.521	—
	p-value	< .001	—
	Kendall's Tau B	0.466	—
	p-value	< .001	—

Source: Authors own research

Hypothesis number 5 which says: "Students who have experienced negative emotions related to the use of artificial intelligence will have a lower perception of its benefits in their educational process." Was analyzed and the result are the next ones:

- Pearson's r (-0.068): This coefficient indicates a very weak negative correlation between experiencing negative emotions related to the use of artificial intelligence and the perception of its benefits in the educational process among students.
- P-value (0.480): The p-value is greater than the standard significance level of 0.05, indicating that there is no significant correlation between experiencing negative emotions and the perception of benefits.
- Spearman's rho (-0.074): This non-parametric correlation coefficient also confirms a very weak negative correlation, but it is not statistically significant.
- Kendall's Tau B (-0.068): Similarly, this coefficient indicates a very weak negative correlation, further supporting the lack of a significant relationship between experiencing negative emotions and the perception of benefits.

The results of the bivariate analysis do not support hypothesis 5. There is no significant correlation between students' experience of negative emotions related to the use of artificial intelligence and their perception of its benefits in the educational process.

Consequently, hypothesis 5 is refuted based on the correlation coefficients and p-values obtained from the analysis. These findings suggest that experiencing negative emotions related to the use of artificial intelligence does not necessarily result in a lower perception of its benefits in the educational process.

Table 4. Correlations for hypothesis number 5

Correlation Table 5b

Variable	Benefits Emotions		
1. Benefits	Pearson's r	—	
	p-value	—	
	Spearman's rho	—	
	p-value	—	
	Kendall's Tau B	—	
	p-value	—	
2. Emotions	Pearson's r	-0.068	—
	p-value	0.480	—
	Spearman's rho	-0.074	—
	p-value	0.443	—
	Kendall's Tau B	-0.068	—
	p-value	0.441	—

Source: Authors own research

Regarding Hypothesis 6 which says "There is an association between the degree of concern among students about the negative effects of artificial intelligence and their level of use of these technologies in studies.", an analysing was conducted and the result are the following:

- Pearson's r (0.029): This coefficient indicates a very weak positive correlation between the degree of concern about the negative effects of artificial intelligence and the level of use of these technologies in studies among students.
- P-value (0.767): The p-value is greater than the standard significance level of 0.05, indicating that there is no significant correlation between the degree of concern and the level of use of AI technologies.
- Spearman's rho (0.007): This non-parametric correlation coefficient also indicates a very weak positive correlation between the degree of concern and the level of use of AI technologies, but it is not statistically significant.
- Kendall's Tau (0.004): Similarly, this coefficient indicates a very weak positive correlation, but it is not statistically significant.

The results of the correlation analysis do not support hypothesis 6. There is no significant correlation between the degree of concern among students about the negative effects of artificial intelligence and their level of use of these technologies in studies.

Therefore, hypothesis 6 is refuted based on the correlation coefficients and p-values obtained from the analysis. These findings suggest that students' concerns about the negative effects of artificial intelligence do not necessarily influence their usage of these technologies in their studies.

Table 5. Correlations for hypothesis number 6

	Pearson		Spearman		Kendall	
	r	p	rho	p	tau B	p
Level of concern - Frequency	0.029	0.767	0.007	0.942	0.004	0.956

Source: Authors own research

5. DISCUSSION

Overall, the study found that AI writing tools, particularly ChatGPT, are widely used among students, with varying degrees of acceptance and ethical consideration. While some students view them as unfair shortcuts that undermine academic integrity, others see them as convenient aids that streamline the writing process. The differing perspectives underscore the need for nuanced approaches to regulation and ethical guidelines in academic settings.

Limitations of the study include the relatively small sample size and the potential for participant bias, particularly in the qualitative phase. Future research could explore the prevalence of different student typologies on a larger scale and investigate the effectiveness of educational interventions aimed at promoting ethical AI use.⁵

6. CONCLUSIONS

The research presented in this article aimed to explore the perceptions and behaviours of students regarding the use of AI-based digital writing tools in academic settings, as well as the relationship between such usage and plagiarism. Through both qualitative and quantitative research methods, a comprehensive understanding of this complex issue was sought.

The theoretical framework provided insight into the growing impact of AI language models in both business and academic environments, raising ethical questions regarding their use in academic projects and the need for regulatory measures within universities.

The qualitative research phase, conducted through focus groups, revealed distinct typologies of student attitudes towards AI writing tools. These ranged from outright rejection due to perceived unfairness and ethical concerns, to flexible acceptance with awareness of ethical considerations, and finally to a pragmatic embrace of technology-driven academic practices.

In the quantitative research phase, hypotheses were formulated and tested to determine the correlation between various factors such as familiarity with AI technologies, frequency of use, academic performance, and perceptions of efficacy and ethical concerns. The findings provided valuable insights into the nuanced relationship between these variables.

In conclusion, this research contributes to the ongoing dialogue surrounding the ethical implications of AI technologies in academia. By shedding light on student perceptions and behaviours, it provides valuable insights for policymakers, educators, and researchers seeking to navigate the complex landscape of AI-driven academic practices.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to our colleagues and mentors at The Bucharest University of Economics Studies for their invaluable support and guidance throughout this research. We also extend our appreciation to the students who participated in the focus groups and surveys, providing critical insights that shaped the findings of this study. Finally, we acknowledge the journal's reviewers for their constructive feedback, which helped to refine this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] Johnson, A. (2019). Automated Grading Systems in Higher Education: Benefits and Challenges. *Educational Technology Review*, 28(1), 67-82.
- [2] Johnson, A. (2020). Interdisciplinary Research on AI Ethics and Education: Opportunities and Challenges. *Journal of Higher Education Management*, 15(2), 78-91.
- [3] Johnson, A. (2021). Overcoming Resistance to AI Adoption in Higher Education. *Journal of Higher Education Management*, 15(2), 78-91.
- [4] Johnson, A. (2022). Promoting Equity in AI Education: Strategies for Mitigating Bias and Discrimination. *Journal of Higher Education Management*, 15(2), 78-91.
- [5] Johnson, A., & Wang, L. (2020). The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Higher Education. *Journal of Higher Education Management*, 15(2), 78-91.
- [6] Jones, C. (2021). The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Interactive Learning Environments. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 18(2), 45-62.
- [7] Jones, C., & Wang, L. (2019). Addressing Bias in AI Algorithms: Implications for Higher Education. *Educational Technology Review*, 28(1), 67-82.
- [8] Jones, C., & Wang, L. (2020). Partnerships for AI Innovation in Higher Education: Lessons Learned and Future Directions. *Educational Technology Review*, 28(1), 67-82.
- [9] Jones, C., & Wang, L. (2020). Transparency and Accountability in AI Decision-Making: A Framework for Ethical AI in Education. *Educational Technology Review*, 28(1), 67-82. Li, X., & Jones, C. (2018). AI Tutoring Systems: A Review of Recent Advances and Future Directions. *Educational Technology Review*, 26(4), 78-91.
- [10] Li, X., & Jones, C. (2018). Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Higher Education. *International Journal of Educational Technology*, 12(4), 123-140.
- [11] Li, X., & Jones, C. (2019). Engaging Stakeholders in AI Governance: Challenges and Strategies. *International Journal of Educational Technology*, 12(4), 123-140.
- [12] Li, X., & Jones, C. (2018). Ethical Considerations in the Adoption of AI in Higher Education. *International Journal of Educational Technology*, 12(4), 123-140.
- [13] Li, X., & Jones, C. (2018). Ethical Guidelines for AI Development in Education. *International Journal of Educational Technology*, 12(4), 123-140.

- [14] Smith, J. (2019). Addressing Bias in AI Algorithms: Implications for Higher Education. *Educational Technology Review*, 25(3), 45-62. Smith, J. (2019). Artificial Intelligence in Education: Promises and Pitfalls. *Educational Technology Review*, 25(3), 45-62.
- [15] Smith, J. (2020). Enhancing Student Learning Through Personalized Education. *International Journal of Educational Technology*, 15(3), 123-140.
- [16] Smith, J. (2019). Integrating AI Ethics into Higher Education Curriculum. *Educational Technology Review*, 25(3), 45-62.
- [17] Smith, J. (2019). The Challenges of Implementing AI in Higher Education. *Educational Technology Review*, 25(3), 45-62.

Citation: Giulia-Elena Zaharia, Ingrid-Georgeta Apostol and Iuliana Cetina, The Overlooked Effects of Artificial Intelligence in Higher Education: A Critical Analysis, *International Journal of Marketing and Human Resource Management (IJMHRM)*, 15(2), 2024, pp. 116–132.

Abstract Link: https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJMHRM_15_02_010

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJMHRM/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_2/IJMHRM_15_02_010.pdf

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

editor@iaeme.com